

Covid-19 Pandemic and Axiology of Communication: A Study of Linguistic Phenomena

Sukmawaty¹, Fakhriawan Fathu Rahman², Citra Andini³

^{1,2,3}Faculty of Cultural Sciences, Hasanuddin University, Makassar, Indonesia

Abstract:- This study aims to determine the intensity of the birth of terms and absorption of words related to the topic of the Covid-19 pandemic. The birth of a number of these terms is in line with the incessant news regarding the Covid-19 pandemic which must be immediately disseminated to the public. The obstacles that occur in the news are a number of foreign terms that are not immediately understood by the public. As a result, this condition forces the birth of a number of terms and absorption words that can make it easier for readers to understand the contents of the reading. Data collection was carried out for two years from March 2000 to February 2002. Based on this research, it was found that Indonesian as the state language has its own system or rules that must be obeyed by its speakers. Therefore, all words or terms that enter Indonesia must comply with these rules. To achieve this goal, here the author uses a qualitative descriptive method with a content analysis approach. The data in this study were sourced from written news sources and through TV, YouTube and online news media. regarding the Covid-19 pandemic. This study uses three stages of data analysis, namely the stage of data reduction, data presentation, and drawing conclusions. The results of the study found that almost all absorptions (medical, social, economic and political terms). This matching and translation were carried out to fill in the blanks of terms and form their equivalents in order to achieve fast and accurate information delivery.

Keywords:- Acceptability, Terms, Content Analysis, Matching, Borrowing

I. INTRODUCTION

The need for rapid and precise dissemination of information requires a fast and precise communication strategy as well. With the use of informative language, the delivery of information can be useful for readers or listeners. Language is the most perfect and effective communication tool used by humans to interact. Tarigan (2009:4); Rahman, (2022) suggests that humans use language as a vital communication tool in this life. This statement emphasizes the main function of language in life as the delivery of information, hopes, criticisms, and ideas to form certain discourses in society. Communication as a means of exchanging information between two or more people can work well when using the right communication methods. Usually language is used as a medium to communicate with other people in the environment and society. In addition, in communicating they use various languages that they understand and understand each other.

There are two kinds of communication, namely direct and indirect communication. According to Yunita (2010),

direct communication is a communication that is done face to face, and is generally done orally, while indirect communication is a communication that is delivered through media that is considered effective. Indirect communication requires media as a means to transform ideas and messages. This is where the role of language is needed.

It must be admitted that in its development, language cannot be separated from the dynamic nature contained in the nature of language itself. That is, language is inseparable from the possibility to change and develop. Changes and language development can occur at the phonological, morphological, syntactic, and semantic levels (Orong: 2017). Or in other words, changes and developments that occur affect the structure of language. The structure of language includes the fields of: sound, form, and sentence structure (Djawa, et al., 2020).

Based on the current situation, especially regarding to the Covid-19 pandemic, it is clear that the dynamic nature of language is very pronounced. With the outbreak of the Covid-19 pandemic, new terms have also spread in people's lives, in Indonesia for example. These terms are generally terms from and influenced by foreign languages. The forms also vary, single vocabulary, word combinations, abbreviations, and some are in the form of acronyms. Foreign terms such as droplet, suspect, lockdown, social distancing, local transmission, WFH (work from home), and so on. The birth of the term is intended to meet the needs of communication and the provision of information.

In addition, the presence of these terms will immediately fill in new terms and vocabulary to meet communication needs. The author considers this match important so that all Indonesian language users can understand and understand terms related to the Covid-19 pandemic so that it is accepted by the community.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

This article examines a number of data units obtained from various sources related to the emergence of various terms, especially during the pandemic. For example, the article entitled "Characteristic Patterns of Variety of Terms During the Covid-19 Pandemic (Coronavirus Disease) written by Oktavia and Hayati(2019) only focuses on grouping terms during the Covid-19 pandemic and the meaning or purpose of these terms. The grouping of terms is used as a reference in this paper, but what distinguishes this article from this article is the addition of an explanation regarding the acceptance of these terms in Indonesian society. the pandemic that became the object of discussion was "Health Registration of the Covid-19 Pandemic Era in Communication in Various Online Media" by Junieles, (2020); "Covid-19, Speech and Cultural

Change” by Misbah, (2021).”; “The Existence of Indonesian in a Pandemic Period” by Devianty (2020); and “Covid-19 and Changes in Social Communication by Dani and Mediantara, (2020). The four articles all use the term during the Covid-19 pandemic as the object of discussion. However, the difference between this article and this paper lies in the discussion of the acceptance of these terms in the general public.

An article that also discusses terms during the Covid-19 pandemic is in an article entitled "The Contribution of Indonesian Language in Controlling Covid-19" by Pranowo "Ellipsis on Covid-19 Discourse in the Opinion Column of Kompas Newspaper" by Pranowo, (2020). However, these two articles discuss terms and their relationship at the sentence level and theoretical analysis that is different from this article. Articles that use the same theory and have similar but different objects of discussion are “The Acceptance of Indonesian Terms” by Andi Sukri (2011); “Entailment and Implicature Analysis in Advertising Language (In Pragmatic Studies)” by Aryani (2016); and “Approaching Discourse Analysis” by Ibn Hamad. These three articles have similarities and similarities in the use of theory with this paper. In addition to referring to the articles above, this paper also uses theories that are considered relevant in terms of acceptance research and discourse analysis. The following are several theories related to writing, including acceptability, discourse analysis; language functions, and terms.

The concept of acceptability is related to grammar. Syamsuri (2011:110); Rahman, (2011). The term acceptable is a primitive or prascientific term, but is still used to distinguish between grammatical and meaningful things. An acceptable expression is something that has been said in a certain context by a speaker and can be accepted by speakers of another language. Lyons further states that there are three possibilities regarding certain inaccuracies in a language, namely as follows: a) accent errors (foreign speakers), even though grammatically. His accent seems odd to native speakers; b) grammatical but not meaningful; and c) grammatical and meaningful, but not obscene, for example swearing; thus, socially unacceptable.

Meanwhile, according to Sunaryo and Adiwimarta (2000:223), these two experts mention the principle of efficiency and the principle of intertransibility. This principle is stated as a benchmark for acceptance of the term Indonesian. The principle of efficiency is that the absorption of short and easy-to-pronounce foreign terms can be carried out by the absorber through spelling adjustments or absorption of the basic form for the purposes of the Vedic system, et al., (2021); Rahman & Rahman (2019). The principle of untranslatability is that it is easy for language users to trace the original form of terms and recognize the original terms and concept meanings. Furthermore, Gunawan, (1996) conducted a study on the level of acceptance of the new term in respondents with higher education. The results of his research show that the acceptance of the new term in an educated society is subject to usefulness, economy, and beauty. The usability aspect is the stability of terms that are useful for explaining the intent

and meaning clearly without causing confusion and ambiguity. From the opinions of these experts, it can be stated that the acceptability of a term can be seen from several sides, namely effectiveness, efficiency, standardization, translation into modern languages, usability, politeness, and contextual aspects.

A. Term

There are several opinions regarding the term, including Putra, et al., (2017:37) stating that in terms of terminology a term is a word or phrase used as a name or symbol that states which of these terms. This term is often referred to as vocabulary which is the whole word that is in one's memory and will cause a reaction after being read and heard by Rahman (2019). It can be said that a term is a word or can be interpreted as a combination of words that function as an expression of a matter, process, concept, or feature that characterizes a particular field.

The opinion above is expanded by Hariyanto (2010: 296) that terms or vocabulary are all words that have been heard by speakers that have been compiled like a dictionary and are accompanied by brief and complete explanations so that they are easily understood by readers. The word is just the smallest unit that can stand alone and has the meaning of the word.

Vocabulary is a set of words that are owned by someone or another tribe and are part of a particular language (Waridah, 2018:113). On the other hand, Susanti (2016: 229) adds that vocabulary is used to collect all the words understood by a person or words that are likely to be used by someone to construct new sentences.

III. OBJECTIVES OF STUDY

The purpose of this study was formulated; 1) to determine the intensity of the emergence of terms and borrowing of words related to the Covid-19 pandemic topic, and 2) to map the aspects and forms of absorption of vocabulary in Indonesian.

IV. METHOD

The research method in this paper uses a qualitative descriptive approach, namely problem-solving procedures by describing the state of the research object based on the facts that appear as they are (Sugiyono, 2013). The source of qualitative research data is the display of spoken or written words observed by researchers and objects observed in detail so that the meaning implied in the document or object can be captured. The data is in the form of qualitative as stated in the words of Rahman, (2017). The author conducted a content analysis by providing a description of the research in the form of a description (Arikunto, 2010:22). The subject in this study is the term Covid-19 virus. The object of this research is the acceptance of terms that are focused on terms during the Covid-19 pandemic.

The technique used in this research is the technique of observation and data collection. The observation technique is carried out directly without any intermediary in data

acquisition. Data collection was carried out by filtering documents from data that had been collected based on data sources in the form of written data regarding various language terms during the Covid-19 pandemic as research analysis material.

V. DATA SOURCES AND DATA ANALYSIS METHODS

There are two parts to this section, they are data source and analysis method;

A. Data source

This research data comes from several sources, including online media, newspapers, government announcements, articles

B. Analysis Method

The data in this study were analyzed using a categorical method, namely grouping data units according to the principle of language borrowing. Language borrowing consists of naturally.

VI. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

A. Finding

This study found that as many as 65 units of data were very productively used in the Covid-19 discourse. The following is a table of the data in question along with the absorption forms, and the context of their meaning in Indonesian.

No	English	Indonesian	Remark
1	Home Isolation	Isolasi Mandiri	suatu upaya untuk memisahkan orang yang terkonfirmasi COVID-19 dari orang yang sehat
2	Mask	Masker	masker medis tersedia dalam berbagai level ketebalan dan untuk melindungi serta mencegah masuknya virus saat menghirup oksigen
3	Vaccine	Vaksin	Vaksin adalah zat atau senyawa yang berfungsi untuk membentuk kekebalan tubuh terhadap suatu penyakit.
4	quarantine	Karantina	tempat pengasingan atau tindakan sebagai upaya pencegahan masuk dan tersebar nyahama dan penyakit atau organisme pengganggu dari luar
5	ventilator	ventilator	sebuah mesin yang berfungsi untuk menunjang atau membantu pernapasan seseorang sehingga mampu bernapas orang normal.
6	respirator	alat pernafasan	untuk mencegah pemakaian menghirup kontaminan berbahaya yang tercampur di udara seperti partikel virus dan bakteri
7	zoonosis	Zoonosis	jenis penyakit yang dapat ditularkan hewan ke manusia.
8	antiseptic	Antiseptic	senyawa kimia yang digunakan untuk membunuh atau menghambat pertumbuhan mikroorganisme pada jaringan yang hidup seperti pada permukaan kulit
9	chloroquine	Klorokuin	obat yang digunakan untuk mencegah dan mengobati malaria
10	corona suspect	terduga korona; suspek korona	suspek memiliki salah satu atau beberapa kriteria COVID-19
11	corona virus	virus korona	mengakibatkan terjadinya infeksi saluran pernapasan atas ringan hingga sedang, seperti penyakit flu.
12	cross contamination	kontaminasi silang	perpindahan mikroorganisme berbahaya ke makanan dan minuman lain
13	decontamination	Dekontaminasi	upaya kesehatan yang dilakukan untuk mengurangi atau menghilangkan kontaminasi oleh mikroorganisme pada manusia
14	disinfectant	Disinfektan	agen antimikroba yang dirancang untuk menonaktifkan atau menghancurkan mikroorganisme pada permukaan lembab.
15	droplet	Percikan	cairan atau cipratan liur yang dikeluarkan seseorang dari hidung atau mulut saat bersin, batuk, bahkan berbicara.
16	face shield	pelindung wajah	Face Shield merupakan salah satu jenis Alat Pelindung Diri (APD) yang

			digunakan untuk melindungi wajah.
17	flattening the curve	pelandaiankurva	upaya memperlambat penyebaran penyakit menular
18	hand sanitizer	penyanyitasitangan	produk pembersihan berbasis alkohol yang bisa berbentuk gel atau cairan
19	hazmat suit	alat pelindung diri (APD)	Alat Pelindung Diri (APD) yang terdiri atas sebuah pakaian yang meliputi seluruh tubuh
20	herd immunity	kekebalan kelompok	kekebalan masyarakat dari penyakit
21	imported case	kasus impor	penularan virus Corona kepada individu yang baru kembali dari luar wilayah tempat tinggal
22	incubation	inkubasi	proses pertumbuhan
23	local transmission	penularan lokal	penemuan sumber infeksi yang diidentifikasi di suatu wilayah
24	lockdown	karantina wilayah	upaya pengendalian penyebaran infeksi
25	massive test	tes serentak	tes besar-besaran
26	new normal	kenormalan baru	langkah percepatan penanganan COVID-19 dalam bidang kesehatan, sosial, dan ekonomi. Skenario new normal dijalankan dengan mempertimbangkan kesiapan daerah dan hasil riset epidemiologi di wilayah terkait.
27	Pandemic	Pandemi	epidemi yang menyebar ke berbagai negara lain dan memengaruhi orang di seluruh dunia dalam jumlah besar secara simultan atau berkelanjutan
28	physical distancing	menjaga jarak fisik	pembatasan jarak manusia secara fisik
29	Protocol	Protokol	serangkaian aturan yang dikeluarkan oleh pemerintah
30	rapid strep test	uji strep cepat	tes deteksi antigen cepat (RADT) untuk membantu dalam diagnosis faringitis
31	Respirator	Respirator	alat yang ditutupkan ke hidung atau mulut untuk membantu pernapasan
32	Screening	penyaringan	tindakan awal yang dilakukan petugas kesehatan terhadap pasien yang datang ke rumah sakit.
33	self-isolation	isolasi mandiri	tindakan pencegahan efektif yang dilakukan untuk melindungi diri dan orang-orang di sekitarnya agar tidak tertular virus corona
34	self-quarantine	swakarantina; karantina mandiri	kegiatan untuk mengkarantina diri sendiri yang dilakukan selama 14 hari
35	social distancing	penjarakan sosial; jarak sosial	sebagai bentuk usaha non-formasi untuk mengontrol penyebaran wabah seperti COVID-19.
36	social media distancing	penjarakan media sosial	menjaga jarak dan membatasi interaksi dengan informasi buruk di media sosial.
37	swab test	uji usap	salah satu metode yang dilakukan oleh tenaga medis untuk mendeteksi keberadaan virus atau bakteri
38	PCR (Polymerase Chain Reaction) test	PCR (Polimerase Reaksi berantai) tes	tes ada atau tidaknya virus Korona dalam tubuh
39	thermo gun	pistol termometer	alat yang mengukur temperatur atau suhu tanpa bersentuhan dengan obyek yang akan diukur suhunya
40	throat swab test	tes usap tenggorokan	tindakan medis yang digunakan untuk mengambil sampel dari tenggorokan pasien agar dapat mengidentifikasi adanya patogen

			penyebabinfeksi.
41	Tracing	penelusuran; pelacakan	konsepuntukmendeteksi orang-orang yang berpotensi terinfeksi virus dari pasien positif Covid-19.
42	work from home (WFH)	kerjadarirumah (KDR)	melakukanpekerjaandarirumah, dan salah satu cara bagi perusahaan di seluruh dunia untuk mengurangi potensi infeksi Covid-19.
43	work from office	kerjadarikantor (KDK)	format pembagian kerjadengan mempertimbangkan protokol kesehatan di era pandemi
44	Lockdown	Karantina Wilayah	suatu upaya pengendalian penyebaran infeksi
45	Persons Under Monitoring (PUM)	Pasiendalampengawasan (PDP)	orang yang mungkin terinfeksi virus korona
46	asymptomatic	Orang tanpa gejala (OTG)	orang yang positif terinfeksi virus Corona tetapi tidak mengalami gejala atau gejalanya sangat ringan
47	Herd immunity	kekebalan kelompok	kekebalan masyarakat dari penyakit, baik secara alamiah maupun setelah divaksin
48	Large-Scale Social Restrictions	Pembatasan Sosial Berskala Besar (PSBB)	pembatasan kegiatan di luar rumah
49	close contact	kontak erat	berdekatan atau berinteraksi dengan pasien
50	clinical trial	uji klinis	pengujian obat baru
51	cluster	klaster	tempat asal penyebaran virus Korona di suatu wilayah
52	comorbidity	komorbiditas atau penyakit bawaan	penyakit yang sedang diderita
53	community transmission	penularan di masyarakat	penularan virus Korona yang terjadi di tengah masyarakat
54	confirmed cases	kasus terkonfirmasi	jumlah orang yang terinfeksi virus Korona
55	contact tracing	riwayat kontak	tinggal serumah atau sering bertemu
56	direct transmission	penularan langsung (virus Korona)	penularan virus dari seseorang ke orang lain melalui percikan ludah/ingus yang masuk ke mata, hidung, atau mulut.
57	epidemic	epidemi	wabah yang menyebar luas di suatu negara
58	epicentrum	titik pusat penyebaran (virus Korona)	titik pusat penyebaran (virus Korona)
59	extraordinary event	Kejadian Luar Biasa (KLB)	status peringatan pemerintah sebelum terjadi wabah
60	healthcare workers	tenaga kerja kesehatan (Tenakes)	tenaga kerja kesehatan
61	high-risk group (Covid-19)	kelompok rentan (virus Korona)	anggota masyarakat yang mudah terinfeksi virus Korona
62	positive for Covid-19	- positif Covid-19 - positif virus Korona - positif Korona - positif terinfeksi virus Korona	terinfeksi virus Korona
63	stay at home/ shelter in place	tetap di rumah	di rumah saja

Table 1: Covid-19 discourse

The data shows that the absorption element in this study only focuses on the absorption element from English to Indonesian in terms of related to Covid-19.

No	Terms	Borrowing		
		1	2	3
1	Incubation: inkubasi	√		
2	Epidemic: epidemi			√
3	Lockdown: Karantinawilayah			√
4	Massive test: Tesserentak			√
5	New normal: Kenormalanbaru			√
6	Protocol: protokol	√		
7	Swab test: uji usap			√
8	Thermo gun: pistol termometer			√
9	Throat swab test: tesusaptenggorokan			√
10	Tracing: pelacakan			√
11	Work from home (WFH): kerjadarirumah (KDR)			√
12	Chloroquine: Klorokuin	√		
13	Herd immunity: kekebalankelompok			√
14	Disinfectant: desinfektan	√		
15	Work from office: kerjadarikantor (KDK)			√
16	asymptomatic: Orang tanpagejala (OTG)			√
17	Large-Scale Social Restrictions: PembatasanSosialBerskalaBesar (PSBB)			√
18	Airborne transmission: penularanmelaluiudara			√
19	close contact: kontakterat, clinical trial: uji klinis			√
20	community transmission: penularan di masyarakat			√
21	Ventilator: Ventilator		√	
22	Self-quarantine: karantinamandiri			√
23	Respirator: respirator		√	
24	Home Isolation: IsolasiMandiri			√
25	Mask: Masker			√
26	PCR(Polymerase ChainReaction) test: tes PCR			√
27	Vaccine: Vaksin			√
28	Quarantine: Karantina			√
29	Zoonosis: zoonosis		√	
30	Corona suspect: Terduga korona			√
31	Corona virus: Virus Korona			√
32	Crosscontamination: Kontaminasi Silang			√
33	Droplet: Percikan			√
34	Face shield: Pelindungwajah			√
35	Flattening the curve: Pelandaiankurva			√
36	Hand sanitizer: Penyitasitangan			√
37	Hazmat suit: Alatpelindungdiri			√
38	Decontamination:dekontaminasi	√		
39	Imported case: Kekebalankelompok			√
40	Local transmission: penularan local			√
41	Antiseptic: Antiseptik	√		
42	Physical distancing: Menjagajarakfisik			√
43	Rapid strep test: uji strep cepat			√
44	Screening: penyaringan			√
45	Self-isolation: isolasimandiri			√
46	Social distancing: jagajarak social			√
47	Social media distancing: jagajarak media sosial			√
48	Cluster: klaster	√		
49	healthcare workers: tenagakerjakesehatan (Tenakes)			√
50	high-risk group (Covid-19): kelompokrentan (virus Korona)			√
51	positive for Covid-19: positif Korona			√
52	Stay at home/shelter in place: tetap di rumah			√

53	healthcare workers: tenagakerjakesehatan (Tenakes)			√
54	high-risk group (Covid-19): kelompokrentan (virus Korona)			√
55	positive for Covid-19: positif Korona			√
56	Stay at home/shelter in place: tetap di rumah			√
57	confirmed cases: kasusterkonfirmasi			√
58	contact tracing: riwayatkontak			√
59	direct transmission: penularanlangsung			√
60	extraordinary event: KejadianLuarBiasa (KLB)			√
61	asymptomatic: Orang tanpagejala (OTG)			√
62	Comorbidit: komorbiditas	√		
63	Large-Scale Social Restrictions: PembatasanSosialBerskalaBesar (PSBB)			√

Table 2: Borrowing words from English to Indonesian in terms Covid-19

*) legend: 1 Adaptation, 2 Adoption, 3 Translation

B. Discussion

There are quite a number of terms that have emerged during the Covid-19 pandemic and most of them are new terms. The diversity of terms and their uniqueness is very interesting to study. In this discussion section, all data units are grouped and their meanings. In addition, an explanation of the context of its use for the general public is also added. The grouping of loans is as follows.

The distribution of loans can be seen as follows;

Fig. 1: The distribution of loans words

Based on the description in the discussion, by looking at the trend in the lending aspect, this study concludes as follows:

The translation aspect shows the highest number among the borrowing aspects, namely 48 (81%), while the adaptation aspect is 8 (14%) and Adoption 3 (5%). This shows that the COVID-19 pandemic has given birth to several new terms that are already widely used in society. Of course, there is a strong reason why borrowing is dominated by translation, because the translation process is a fast process compared to the other two categories, namely adaptation and adoption. Adaptation category takes time, while adaptation is sometimes difficult to use and socialize.

In the midst of the outbreak of the Corona virus infection (COVID-19), various terms related to this disease emerged, ranging from social distancing, lockdown, Droplet, and several terms as mentioned in the previous discussion. Currently the world is being shocked by the outbreak of COVID-19. How not, the disease caused by this latest type of corona virus has claimed thousands of lives. In an effort to suppress the spread of the Corona virus, the government urges people to practice social distancing. 'social distancing' or 'social distancing' is avoiding public places, staying away from crowds, and maintaining an optimal distance of two meters from other people. With the distance, the spread of this disease is expected to be reduced. In addition, there is another term that is very familiar due to the emergence of the COVID-19 outbreak, namely lockdown. What is meant by "lockdown" is regional quarantine, namely restrictions on the movement of residents in an area, including closing access to and from entering and leaving the area. Closure of entry and exit routes as well as restrictions on population movement are carried out to reduce contamination and spread of COVID-19 disease.

The Indonesian language policy carried out by the government by providing various equivalent foreign terms related to the corona pandemic is a very good effort. Therefore, it is necessary to look at the development of the implementation of the Indonesian equivalent policy for various foreign terms and from the aspect of borrowing words related to corona. After the outbreak of the epidemic, the way humans work was also affected, that's why the term Work from Home (WFH) emerged. The work system that used to be able to gather and have to come to the office turned into part of the work done at home. Meanwhile (WFH) is equivalent to Work From Home (KDR) and Work From Office (WFO) is equivalent to Work From Office (KDK). Several terms have also emerged due to the outbreak of the Covid-19 outbreak.

After the emergence of these foreign terms, now there is such a thing as New Normal. The corona virus pandemic gave birth to a new habit called a new term, namely the New Normal. This term has become a new habit in various sectors of human life where humans have to get used to using masks (masks), face shields as mentioned in the previous discussion, and doing social or physical distancing wherever they are.

Various sectors of life such as industry, education, tourism, the economy and various other fields must continue to run as before the pandemic, this is what is meant by the new normal. These terms are widely used on the internet, including on social media, and new vocabulary or terms appear, therefore it can be said that vocabulary development is very dynamic in accordance with the development and needs of language users.

VII. CONCLUSION

After discussing the data collected as many as 34 data terms during the Covid-19 pandemic, the authors get several conclusions. This conclusion is expected to provide a good understanding to the readers. From the results of the discussion, it is known that most of the terms related to the Covid-19 pandemic come from English. This is a natural thing because it is an epidemic that spreads throughout the world or is called a pandemic and is handled internationally. English certainly plays an important role in conveying this virus to all citizens of the world. However, this does not mean that Indonesian does not contribute to the speaking community regarding this pandemic. Our language also gives rise to several new terms according to the needs of handling cases of this pandemic. In addition, Indonesian also matches almost all English terms into Indonesian. Matching, of course, is guided by the linguistic rules and linguistic rules that we already have. Hopefully this simple article can be useful for readers and writers, please provide input for the improvement of the next work.

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